

HOW TO MEASURE INTANGIBLE RESOURCES IN LISTED COMPANIES¹

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ABSTRACT

The principal problems associated with the concept of intellectual capital (except for the lack of recognized definition) includes the lack of a recognized standard of valuation. This prevents investors and other stakeholders to compare companies in the markets. Most studies concerning the measurement of intangible resources relates to companies in such industries as biotechnology, aerospace, computer software, cosmetics, healthcare, Internet, media, advertising, pharmaceuticals and computer industry. The main goal of this paper is to present advantages and disadvantages of most popular intellectual capital valuation ratios which can be used in listed companies.

KEYWORDS

Intangible resources, Intellectual Capital, listed companies, intangibles valuation,

JEL CLASSIFICATION CODES

G32, O3, O16

1. INTELLECTUAL CAPITAL VALUATION RATIOS

Functioning of companies on the market under conditions of high volatility environment necessitates the use of modern methods and instruments of financial management. In the capital market should not be considered the intangible resources (also called - intellectual capital) as a value added. Intellectual capital (IC) is the absolute requirement of allowing firms to compete. The high level of IC and its effective management determines the firm's strong competitive position and, consequently, the construction of its value. To manage the IC there is necessary to use valuation tools. Currently there is no recognized standard for IC valuation, which means that the measurement is the hardest part of the complex process of managing IC of the listed company. Based on the analysis of the literature methods of IC valuation of companies can be attributed to four categories[1][2][3]:

I. Market Capitalization Methods – MCM: MV/BV (*Market Value to Book Value ratio*), MVA (*Market Value Added*), q-Tobin's ratio, IAMVTM (*Investor Assigned Market Value*), Invisible Balance Sheet, FiMIAM (*Financial method of intangible assets measurement*).

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II. Return on Assets Methods – ROAM: EVA[®] (*Economic Value Added*[®]), CIV (*Calculated Intangible Value*), KCE[™] (*Knowledge Capital Earnings*[™]), VAIC[™] (*Value Added of Intellectual Coefficient*[™]).

III. Direct Intellectual Capital Methods – DICM: *Technology Broker*, HRCA (*Human Resources Costing and Accounting*), IVM (*Inclusive Valuation Methodology*), IAV (*Intangible Assets Valuation*), TVC[™] (*Total Value Creation*), AFTF[™] (*Accounting for the future*), Citation weighted patents, HR Statement.

IV. Scorecards Methods – SCM: BSC (*Balanced Scorecard*), HCI (ang. *Human Capital Intelligence*), Skandia Navigator[™], VCS[™] (*Value Chain Scoreboard*[™]), IC-Index[™], Business IQ[™], National IC, Holistic Accounts, IC Rating[™], MAGIC, IC – dVAL[™], Danish guidelines, Meritum guidelines, IAM (*Intangible Assets Monitor*), Value Creation Index, Knowledge Audit Cycle.

The first category of methods are indicators based on market capitalization. The rationale for the separation of these methods is to identify the concept of IC as defined by L. Edvinsson [4]. The main advantage of these measures is that these tools can be used to evaluate IC in all listed companies. The second category of indicators are tools based on return on assets. The aim of the methods in this category is the possibility to use the return on intangible assets to evaluate the IC of the firm. The third category is direct measurement of IC. Their main drawback is the attempt of valuation of IC in absolute terms based on a number of definitions of concepts in the literature. The fourth category of IC valuation is scorecard methods. In addition to the Balanced Scorecard methods other models in this group are used in businesses, and details of construction of the indicators are not available. It is worth noting that most of the tools developed to measure the level of IC, the company refers to companies with the financial sector. Thus, because of the availability of data and the specificity of the financial statements of listed companies to realize the main goal of the paper, author has selected the following indicators to analysis: MV/BV (*Market Value to Book Value ratio*); MVA (*Market Value Added*); CIV (*Calculated Intangible Value*); KCE[™] (*Knowledge Capital Earnings*[™]); VAIC[™] (*Value Added of Intellectual Coefficient*[™]).

1.1 Methodology of determining the MV/BV ratio

Ratio MV/BV has been proposed to IC valuation by T. Stewart, and relies on L. Edvinsson's definition of IC [4]. The construction of the ratio is as follows:

$$\frac{MV}{BV} = \frac{\text{Market Value of Equity}}{\text{Book Value of Equity}}$$

Ratio MV/BV as a tool to evaluate of IC has been criticized. Among other things, stated that since the value of IC would be only the value of the difference between market value and the book value of the company, the accounting policy would determine IC level - and it is not. Another disadvantage of this ratio is that the market value based on market price, which may not always reflect the intrinsic value of the company. Very often, the market value is divergent from the fundamental value determined using the DCF valuation model. In some instances (particularly in times of crisis) may be the result of emotions emerging in the stock market. Book value used in the construction of ratio is also not without drawbacks. The book value is determined as of the date of balance sheet and is based on historical cost, which may differ from the present value of the assets. Thus, some authors assume that the existing differences between market value and the book value of equity does not evaluate IC, but merely confirms its existence in the company. However, due to data availability, and ease of calculation this ratio is often used in research on IC. An example of research on intellectual capital using the ratio MV / BV is research of Dipankar Ghosh and Anne Wu [5], who studied the effect of information on the level of intellectual capital on the market value of listed companies.

1.2 Methodology of determining the MVA ratio

The concept of residual income is known since the XVIII century, its key idea is to take into

account the cost of all capitals invested in the company, not just the cost of debt (interest expense). It's was analyzed A. Marshall in 1890 and tried to apply in the 20s and 30 XX century. In the 1990s, the Stern Stewart & Co., affecting significantly the VBM, along with the concept and measure of economic value added (EVA®), introduced at the same time as the market value of (MVA). MVA is estimated at a given time (usually at the end of the year) the difference between the market value of the company and its book value (the value of capital invested in it by the book value):

$$MVA = MV - IC$$

where:

MV - The market value of equity,
IC - Invested capital - book value.

By definition G.B. Stewart's capital invested in this company is the total amount of cash put into the company by investors over its operation and funding of its net assets (total assets minus current liabilities), regardless of their source (own funds or foreign funds), as well as without due to the involvement of business purpose and the treatment of these funds in the accounting system of the company. In practice, however, the estimates of the MVA ratio is used only including equity, given the difficulty of obtaining information about the market value of foreign capital. Thus, MVA can be expressed by the formula:

$$MVA = MV - BV$$

where:

MV - The market value of equity
BV - book value of equity

MVA is a measure of the premium, which the market adds to the book value of equity (or with which the market value of the deducted). In fact, the MVA is measured in terms of units of cash return on committed capital (called cash in - cash out). By author MVA ratio seems to be more appropriate to assess the level of intellectual capital than the MV/BV ratio, which gives a relative indication. The main disadvantage of MVA is to simplify, that the entire value of the difference between market value and book value is equal to the IC. Another problem is the interpretation of negative values of MVA occurs in the long run (because in the short term negative MVA values may result from the stock market panic).

1.3 Methodology of determining the CIV ratio

This ratio was first used in the United States in the 30s XX century and is the first known method for the measurement of intangible assets in companies. T. Stewart, using NCI Research assumptions, shared values of respect CIV process into seven steps:

- Step 1: calculate the average profit before tax for the last three years;
- Step 2: determine the average value of tangible assets for the past three years;
- Step 3: dividing the average return for the past three years by an average value of tangible assets, the result is a rate of return on tangible assets (called ROFA - Return on Fixed Assets):

$$ROFA = \frac{Av. Profit Before Tax}{Av. Fixed Assets}$$

- Step 4: Calculate the average rate of ROFA for the sector (or group of competing companies), in which the company operates for a period of three years (What's important - if the average company ROFA is less than the average sector ROFA cease further estimates),
- Step 5: calculation of the excess return (ER) by multiplying the average ROFA for the sector by the average value of fixed assets the company, then the resulting value is subtracted from the average pre-tax profits for the study of organizations:

$$ER = Gross Profit - (ROFA sector \cdot fixed assets)$$

- Step 6: calculate the average tax rate for the last three years (Tax) and multiplying by the excess return (ER), the result must be subtracted from the amount of ER, the result is a profit that can be attributed to IC (called IP - Intellectual Premium), what else can write the following formula:

$$\text{Intellectual Premium} = ER (1 - \text{Tax})$$

- Step 7: estimating the present value of the IP by dividing it by the discount rate (or cost of capital).

$$\text{CIV} = \frac{\text{Intellectual Premium}}{\text{discount rate}}$$

You can assume a discount rate as a cost of capital, but a more appropriate measure is the rate for IC (at 10.5%, according to research of B. Lev [7], who has set this value to calculate the rate of KCE™). It should be noted that research on the discount rate for the IC or IC expense are fundamentally important for further theoretical discussion of the measurement of IC in listed companies. The advantage of CIV ratio is relative simplicity of calculation. In addition, there is no problem with the availability of data, except that the index is fairly objective measure. Among the critical comments on the substance of CIV ratio can distinguish the saying that in case of a diversified business is required disaggregation of the indicator. In addition, discussion is the dependence of the existence of IC to achieve above average profitability of ROFA in relation to the sector (that would imply that operators of medium or lower profitability of fixed assets do not have the IC, which is not necessarily true). On the other hand, one can assume that in some areas of activity referred to material resources (structural capital) are essential, and only their best use (i.e. the creation of IC) can succeed in a higher yield than that achieved by competitors. Examples of interesting studies on CIV ratio is research of Kujansivu P. and A. Lonnqvist [6] showing the relationship between IC measurement in relative terms (ratio VAIC™) and absolute (CIV ratio).

1.4 Methodology of determining the KCE™ ratio

Knowledge Capital Earnings (KCE™) is a development of CIV indicator. This method was developed by Professor B. Lev - lecturer of Stern Business School (New York) [7]. The starting point of KCE™ indicator is the assumption that the economic output of the company is the sum of the use of physical capital, financial and knowledge capital, which can be represented by the formula:

$$EO = a (PC) + b (FC) + c (KC)$$

where:

EO - The economic output of the company,

PC - physical capital,

FC - financial capital,

KC - intellectual capital,

a, b, c - coefficients of individual capitals.

KCE™ ratio is determined in five stages:

- Step 1: estimate the value of normalized earnings (NE). That is an average earnings from last three years (including the current year), and estimates of earnings for the next three years. It eliminates the short-term fluctuations which distort the further calculations. B. Lev proposes the following algorithm:

$$NE = \frac{E_{t-2} + E_{t-1} + E_t + 2 \cdot (E_t + E_{t+1} + E_{t+2})}{9}$$

Number of years under consideration is a matter of convention. Depends inter alia on the availability of data, or the nature of the industry in which the Company operates. Companies with a

high learning curve (where capital expenditure quickly return) does not require greater numbers of years in order to estimate the NE.

- Step 2: Determine the normalized earnings of the firm resulting from the use of physical capital - NE_{PC} . In order to determine the company's NE_{PC} physical capital (PC)- PC multiplied by the rate of return on physical capital ROPC, as shown in formula:

$$NE_{PC} = PC \cdot ROPC$$

Physical capital is determined by the formula:

$$PC = \text{Fixed Assets} + \text{Stock} - \text{Long-term Liabilities}$$

The rate of return on physical capital ROPC be reflected by the rate of return for the sector in which the company operates. However, B. Lev, on the basis of the study assumes a value of 7%, which represents an annual average rate of return on physical capital to the economy of the United States.

- Step 3: Determination of normalized earnings from the use of the firm's financial capital - NE_{FC} . In order to determine NE_{FC} the financial capital (FC) of the company multiplied by the rate of return on financial capital (ROFC):

$$NE_{FC} = FC \cdot ROFC$$

The financial capital (FC) by the author of KCETM ratio consists of cash, bonds, company shares and financial instruments.

The rate of return on financial capital, according to B. Lev is 4.5%, which represents an annual return of ten-year government bonds in the years 1980-1990 in the USA.

- Step 4: Estimation of normalized earnings generated by the firm's intellectual capital (NE_{IC}) by the formula:

$$NE_{IC} = NE - (NE_{PC} + NE_{FC})$$

- Step 5: Determine the value of KCETM ratio as the quotient of NE_{IC} and ICDR (intellectual capital discount rate):

$$KCE = \frac{NE_{IC}}{ICDR}$$

B. Lev assumes that ICDR stands at 10.5%, and it is an average rate of return on shares in companies and biotechnology companies engaged in software development in the years 1980-1990 in USA.

In addition, the author used a construction of KCETM measurement to evaluate the company through the prism of IC and book value (BV). The sum of KCETM and BV was called by B. Lev as Comprehensive Value:

$$CV = BV + KCE^{TM}$$

where:

CV - Comprehensive Value,

BV - Book value of equity,

KCETM - Knowledge Capital Earnings.

If the MV (market value) > CV it means, according to a study conducted jointly Leva B. of M. Bothwell of CSAM (*Credit Swiss Basset Management*), the company is overvalued by the market. In the opinion of the author of this paper KCETM ratio truly reflects the knowledge capital but does not

necessarily evaluate IC. Moreover, basing the calculation on the basis of the average industry may seem an oversimplification. In addition, it is difficult to prove what portion of the profit results from the use of physical and financial assets.

1.5 Methodology of determining the VAIC™ ratio

Value added of intellectual coefficient (VAIC™) amounts to measure the value added generated by the company. Model determines the extent to which resources of physical capital and intangible impacts on the achievement of that value. The author of this method is A. Pulic (Pulic, 2004). VAIC™ coefficient is the sum of three parameters: CEE (Capital Employed Efficiency), HCE (Human Capital Efficiency), SCE (Structural Capital Efficiency). Thus, the value added intellectual coefficient can be written as follows:

$$VAIC^{TM} = CEE + HCE + SCE$$

The larger the size of the VAIC™ ratio of a company, the better the efficiency of all its resources and greater its value added. A characteristic feature of this method is to estimate the degree of utilization of IC through the use of traditional data from the company's balance sheet. The VAIC™ ratio is determined at five steps:

Step 1: Estimate total value added VA (Value Added). The basis for the calculation were taken profit and loss account, where VA is given by the formula:

$$VA = NOPAT + Am + HC$$

where:

VA - value-added of enterprise,

NOPAT - net operate profit after tax,

Am - depreciation and amortization,

HC - total expenditure on employees (wages and salaries).

One of the more important assumptions in the calculation of the added value of the company is treating the sum of the expenditures on the company's employees in terms of investment and not cost.

• Step 2: Calculate the capital employed efficiency ratio (CEE). It is given by the formula:

$$CEE = \frac{VA}{CE}$$

Increase of this ratio suggests that company is using employed capital more efficient in the creation of its market value.

• Step 3: Determination of the human capital efficiency ratio (HCE). According to A. Pulic human capital corresponds to the general expenses of employees, such as salaries, wages, training, awards. This indicator is therefore calculated as the ratio of total value added, and employment costs:

$$HCE = \frac{VA}{HC}$$

The increase in this ratio reflects improvement of employee productivity, which in turn is transformed into an increase in value throughout the organization.

• Step 4: Determine the size of the structural capital (SC) of the firm. This ratio is calculated by subtracting from the total value-added of the company, value of its human capital HC:

$$SC_i = VA_i - HC_i$$

In business practice, there was observed an inverse relationship between the size of the human capital and the size of the structural capital (SC). On this basis, the efficiency ratio of structural capital (SCE) can be summarized as follows:

$$SCE_i = \frac{SC_i}{VA_i}$$

- Step 5: By summing the indicators listed in steps 2, 3 and 4 there is formed a general indicator of the efficiency of value creation based on the use of tangible and intangible assets of the company:

$$VAIC^{TM} = CEE + HCE + SCE$$

The main advantage of VAICTM ratio is the simplicity of the calculation and the fact that all the necessary data are available in the financial statements of companies. In addition, the indicator allows a comparative analysis between companies operating in the same competitive sector and introducing basic standards for measuring the effectiveness of their activities. But VAICTM ratio has been subjected of criticism. The main objection is that human capital is associated only with employee benefits in the company. However in contrast to MVA, KCETM CIV the VAICTM ratio is an indicator often used by authors of the research to measure the IC level of listed companies.

2. CONCLUSIONS

Not all of the IC valuation ratios identified in the literature are possible for use in listed companies. Most popular (MV/BV, MVA, CIV, KCETM and VAICTM) are often used in research by other authors. The main problem in "how to measure intangible resources in listed companies" is that despite of all advantages and disadvantages of popular IC ratios researchers does not have universal definition of intangible resources (called Intellectual capital). In this point author of this publication poses the question: What is better, evaluate by imperfect indicators very important nowadays (intangible) resource or abandon valuation of Intellectual Capital of listed companies at all?

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